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Coping Strategies on Academic Performance among the OBPETEC College Students

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on what are the coping strategies used by the OBPETEC students of the Philippine Normal University (PNU). The goal is to find out the status of the academic performance of the students, find the most frequently used coping strategies in approach, avoidance, and social support, and lastly find the commonly used coping strategies among all of the coping strategies mentioned. This was done with the help of the Academic Coping Strategy Scale by Dr. Jeremy R. Sullivan (2010) which aims to know the coping strategies used by college students. This research concluded that OBPETEC students are always facing their problems and are always trying to find a way to solve them, also, students always make an effort to have coping strategies for the improvement of their academic performance, and almost all of them avoid doing nothing about the problem, lastly, students rarely communicate with their professors or class advisers to get some social support.

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